

TABLE—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SOME MOAc-Ac₂O PRODUCTS WHICH ARE INFAC T M(OAc, HOAc) ACID SALTS

Compound	Melting Point, °C			C and H percentage of solva'es ¹				C and H percentage calc. by us			
	as in ref. 1	as in litr ⁴	found by us	C		H		for MOAc-Ac ₂ O		for M(OAc, HOAc)	
				Calc	(found)	Calc	(found)	C	H	C	H
Li(OAc, HOAc)	105-7	—	106	36.08	(35.84)	4.49	(4.36)	42.86	6.36	38.09	5.56
Na(OAc, HOAc)	06	—	96	33.33	(33.16)	4.16	(4.02)	39.13	4.89	33.80	4.93
K(OAc, HOAc)	144	144	144	41.08	(40.92)	3.87	(3.64)	36.00	4.50	30.38	4.43
NH ₄ (OAc, HOAc)	66	66	65	34.12	(33.82)	6.16	(6.04)	40.22	7.26	35.01	8.03

Figure. IR spectra of the KOAc-products obtained from (A) the KOAc-Ac₂O system according to ref. 1 and (B) a KOAc-HOAc (1 : 1) reaction in ethanol.

which has been made in an attempt to authentify the products to be MOAc-Ac₂O complexes, is therefore an irrelevant exercise.

For all the four products in question, the "calculated" percentage of elements (see Table) reported by the earlier authors¹ is incorrect even with respect to MOAc-Ac₂O complexes as seen from the comparison of values we report in the Table. It is interestingly significant that their 'found' values have consistently tied up with these incorrectly calculated values and not with the correct values for M⁺(OAc, HOAc)⁻ or MOAc-Ac₂O species that now we are showing in the Table.

The M⁺OAc⁻ salts of Li⁺ and Na⁺ exist as hydrated whereas those of K⁺ and NH₄⁺ are hygroscopic. The authors do not mention about the precautions they took to avoid the involvement of this water during 24 hours of the reaction between MOAc and Ac₂O they carried out¹. This suggests that during "solvate formation" Ac₂O gets hydrolysed to produce HOAc and the latter interacts with M⁺OAc⁻ to produce M(OAc, HOAc) as we found in the present work under controlled conditions in ethanol medium.

We were interested only in the study of the concerned four cations for all of which M(OAc, HOAc) salts instead of MOAc-Ac₂O solvates have been found to form. Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ should be rather more prone to the formation of M(OAc, HOAc) salts because in the presence of these low charge density cations the AcO⁻...HOAc conjugation is expected to be even more facilitated⁷. Therefore, there is no surprise if similar error of inference is made in the case of other products reported in the paper in question.

References

1. K. C. MALHOTRA and D. S. KATOCH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1182.
2. N. S. POONIA, S. SEN, P. K. PORWAL, and A. JAYAKUMAR, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1980, **53**.
3. N. S. POONIA and M. R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1791.
4. R. C. WEAST (Editor-in-chief), "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 46th Edition, The Chemical Rubber Co., Ohio, 1965-66, pp. E-149, B-205.
5. J. CLARE SPEAKMAN, "Structure and Bonding", Volume 12, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1972.
6. D. HADZI, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **11**, 435.
7. N. S. POONIA and A. V. BAJAJ, *Chem. Rev.*, 1979, **79**, 389; N. S. POONIA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1977, **36**, 268.

Paper Chromatographic Studies of Inorganic Ions on Impregnated Paper : Separation of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)

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Manuscript received 22 August 1978, revised 17 July 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

MIGRATION of ions on papers impregnated with 1-phenyl-3-thiobenzoyl thiocarbamide has been studied.

Experimental

Paper strips were first soaked in a sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 5.0 and dried. The papers were then uniformly sprayed with a 2% solution of PTT in acetone. They were dried in an inert atmosphere at room temperature and stored neatly. Spotting of the metal ions was done by a

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micropipette (10 λ). The concentration of metal ions spotted was 10 μ g. Co(II) and Ni(II) form orange red coloured complexes with PTT at pH 5.0 extractable in chloroform. Cu(II) forms a complex at the same pH but is not extractable in any solvent. With PTT impregnated papers, at pH 5.0 copper, nickel and cobalt formed coloured complexes and could be detected without spraying reagents. On untreated papers, they were detected with Rubenic acid (0.5% in ethanol).

Results and Discussion

The experiments were performed with untreated and impregnated paper and R_f data of three metals in different solvents have been collected (Table 1).

TABLE 1— R_f DATA WITH IMPREGNATED AND UNTREATED PAPER

Ion	R_f values $\times 100$					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Cu(II)	0 ; 69*	* ; 67*	0 ; T	0 ; 69*	0 ; T	0 ; -
Ni(II)	80 ; 80*	73 ; 82*	- ; T	75 ; 64*	79 ; T	83 ; -
Co(II)	78 ; 76*	74 ; 76*	- ; T	78 ; 78*	82 ; T	80 ; -
A—Methanol		B—Ethanol		C—Butanol		
D—Acetone		E—Chloroform		F—Methyl ethyl ketone		
*—Diffusion		T—Trailing				

(Values on right are those with untreated paper.)

On the basis of suggested mechanisms^{1,2} for the migration of ions, a metal ion in solution exists as an aquo cation and this can release a proton

This temporarily released proton associates with the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose and ion associated metal cellulose complex is formed. In polar solvents such as alcohols, the reaction taking place may be as follows :

This species formed, however, cannot undergo dissociation to release hydrogen ions for linkage to cellulose structure, resulting in the desorption of metal ion from the cellulose base. The cation now present on the solvent soaked paper moves with the free mobile solvent. This is the expected mechanism in case of a polar solvent with donor properties. But with solvents having no donor properties, formation of ion associated complexes is not possible and hence desorption of metal ion does not take place. This appears to be the reason for migration not taking place with chloroform. Weakly proton donors can bring about the movement of metal ions in the presence of some proton donor (acid) in the medium.

If the solvent is polar enough to replace the water molecules in aquo cation, the presence of optimum concentration of protons may not be essential for migration. However, the presence of protons (as in the present case) will always be useful in getting compact bands or spots and better separation.

In the case of papers impregnated with complexing agent in the stationary phase, process can be described in terms of metal ligand complex formation. On spotting, the metal is fixed on the paper due to metal ligand complex formation. There is no formation of a ion associated metal cellulose complex through hydrogen bond. The metal as complex gets desorbed from the paper and is washed by irrigating solvent on account of its solvating tendencies.

In the case of PTT impregnated paper, protons will be released on complex formation. The released protons may help in the desorbing process as indicated above. In the present work, Cu(II)-PTT complex is completely insoluble in organic solvent and so its migration is not observed. For Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes, the migration can be explained as above.

From the studies, it was clear that the use of PTT impregnated paper can also be made for the separation of Cu from Ni and Co. The investigations were extended to the quantitative separation of Cu from Ni and Co. Papers soaked with buffer of pH 5.0 and PTT were taken and different quantities of metal ions were spotted. Methanol was used as an eluent. After development, the respective spots were treated with concentrated HCl. Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in solutions were then estimated by standard methods (Cu—Diethyldithiocarbamate, Ni—Dimethyl glyoxime and Co—Oxine). PTT did not interfere in the determination.

The PTT impregnated papers thus provide a convenient method for the qualitative and quantitative separation of Cu(II) from Ni(II) and Co(II).

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur for encouragement.

References

1. P. B. JANARDHAN and A. PAUL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 297.
2. R. P. BHATNAGAR and N. P. BHATNAGAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15, 1089.